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Using educational games within the scope of UPSKILLS

UPSKILLS Intellectual output 4.1

Compiled by:
Vanessa Camilleri

* University of Malta

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Executive Summary

The UPSKILLS project finds its scope in providing resources and methods to help the modern linguist and language technology student develop transferable skills and knowledge content in the Language domain. Research shows, that the use of games may support some of the transferable skills identified in UPSKILLS. This report has been divided into three parts.

The first part provides an extensive list of digital games, which lecturers/educators who wish to integrate off-the-shelf games during their lectures or to better direct their course content may use. This comprehensive list of free to use, off-the-shelf games has been compiled, indicating genre, characteristics and scope for the linguistics student profile. In addition to the off-the-shelf games, a quiz-based maze game prototype was created specifically for the project to introduce beginner programmers to concepts in Machine Learning. A number of games developed and created by the Institute of Digital Games for illustrating concepts in Machine Learning have also been included in this list. This list is accompanied by a recommended lesson guide for integrating the games into selected topics or study units in the proposed curricula.

The second part illustrates possible scenarios of how individual games can be included into the linguistics curriculum, through their application for a broader skillset. Recommendations for game play, as well as pre-game and post-game briefing and reflection activities are also included in this section.

The third part describes gamification as a diverse way of applying game principles to learning content, by proposing ideas about how to gamify learning content in a way that is engaging.

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1. Introduction

This report aims to provide a survey of existing game-based practices whilst providing possible scenarios for including specific games into teaching sessions, that are appropriate for language/linguistics training with the use of digital interactive media. Initially it was proposed that games developed by the Institute of Digital Games (IDG) would be included in the UPSKILLS proposed content and curricula. However after an exercise, in the form of a survey, that was designed specifically to determine the needs of the UPSKILLS consortium, it followed that the games proposed initially by the IDG may not fully satisfy the audience's needs.

Following an analysis of the available games, 4 games were proposed as possibly fitting the content developed and created specifically for UPSKILLS. Through discussion with IDG developers it was also noted that changes could not be done to the actual game content and mechanics, and that the game rules and dynamics had to remain the same. However certain elements from the games can still be integrated in lessons that may suit the UPSKILLS consortium.

The first part of the document shows a list of games that have been identified as being in line with the needs of the project consortium as well as the target audience. For this reason our report on 'The language data and project specialist: A new modular profile for graduates in language-related disciplines' (Miličević Petrović et al. 2021) was used as the guiding rationale for matching the language specialist skills identified in the report to the needs of the target audience as emergent from the Game Preference Survey. The emergent list of games, includes 25 off-the-shelf games, that are available freely for download, 4 IDG games that are accessible from the Web, and 2 specifically designed games developed by the University of Malta. The games developed by the University of Malta, include a simple maze game with the scope of reinforcing Machine Learning (ML) concepts, and a retro-style cube game, with the scope of increasing confidence in programming/coding skills, through text-based commands. Both games were developed following the creation of modular content in UPSKILLS which included ML and introduction to programming.

The second part of this document illustrates the proposed scenarios and guidelines for integrating individual games in teaching/learning. Each example is sub-divided into a number of headings, that guide the lecturer/educator, to exploit the game in a way that would support the skill set or outcomes as needed. One important aspect that was taken into consideration for each scenario is the use of pre-game and post-game briefing. The scope of the briefing is that of giving time and space for reflection about the game play, and the outcomes that this play supported. It also serves to facilitate in the students more self-awareness as well as awareness about their skills and competences as accentuated by each game.

The third part of the document illustrates ways and methods in which academics or educators may choose to gamify their learning content. This section also covers the main

differences between gamification and game-based learning and gives examples as to how academics may go about gamifying their teaching.

2. Games for UPSKILLS curricula

2.1 List of games

Tables 1-3 illustrate a list of games that has been compiled specifically for UPSKILLS. The list has been compiled on the basis of the survey results about game preferences by the chosen target audience of linguistics and languages students. However other characterising features for the choice of games included (1) free to play, (2) length of suggested play, (3) skills supported. In addition the expected outcomes from the games identified, could be extended to the domain clusters emergent from the language data and project specialist, that have been identified from the UPSKILLS needs analysis (Miličević Petrović et al. 2021) and refer to categories of the different learning outcomes in terms of knowledge, skills and competences. Since these learning outcomes feature in the design of the curriculum and its individual learning modules, it is assumed that by matching the games to the different clusters would make it easier for the academic/educator to choose games to integrate into their curricular practice.

Name	Description	Publisher	Cost	Accessibility	Players	Language Support	Gameplay Time	Skills	Game Features	UPSKILLS Domain Clusters
Dev Inc.	Creating and Managing a Game Development Company. This game offers a simulation environment, for project management skills. It also helps players reflect about game design practices, and goes into depth for project management skills. The game's narrative revolves around building and maintaining a successful game development company.	Huntah	Free	Windows PC only (available from Steam)	1	1	2-3 hours	Project Management, Game Design, Problem Solving	Narrative/plot	Research-oriented Organisational Transversal
Assignment 42	This is a game which focuses on the use of logic. It offers a basic programming environment, where robots need to be programmed to clear hazard and rescue people inside a building. Creativity in this game is promoted through the use of finding alternative ways of solving problems. This game's narrative revolves around designing and creating solutions to problems within a building in order to rescue people and save lives.	Mindfire	Free	Windows PC only (available from Steam) / Mac OS	1	1	2-3 hours	Problem Solving, Programming basics	Use of Logic/ Programming	Research-oriented Technical Transversal
Tales of Escape	This game can be played either over VR or else from the PC. It is based on the classic escape room mode, where the users (both solo or multiplayer) have to solve a series of quests and puzzles to be able to escape from the room. This game offers users a number of language options, and it also offers an extension to the basic version by integrating a number of additional scenarios at a nominal fee.	OnSkull Games	Free to download (content stories at a nominal price)	Windows PC & VR (Valve, Oculus & HTC Vive)	1-6	11	1-2 hours	Problem solving, player interaction, strategy, communication	Multimodality Multilingual support Individual/ Team choice Problem solving	Research-oriented Transversal
Runescape	This is a fantasy game which is also a Massively Multiplayer Online Role Playing Game. This is a game which involves a degree of strategy but which has an engaging narrative that has kept players returning to play for the past 18 years. It has quests which the players need to solve and can be played both alone or as part of a team. This game can be played either just to explore, and read through the game narrative or plot, or else in a much more extensive, deeper gameplay, where mechanics and rules might be a bit more complex.	Jagex Ltd.	Free to play (certain content is released at a price)	Windows & Mac OS	1-many	4	3+ hours	Problem solving, strategy, social interaction skills	Engaging narrative Multilingual support Individual/ Team choice	Research-oriented Organisational Transversal
Roblox	This game is more popular with children due to its lego-like graphics. However it is a game that has been described by many adults playing it as relaxing. It is essentially a virtual world which contains a number of mini-games, which anyone who has downloaded the game can choose to play. There are games to choose from or all ages. It can contain interactivity, but players can choose to either play individually or else in groups/teams. With its impressive user audience, and millions of games to play, chances are that UPSKILLS target audience are familiar with this game platform and will thus be more accepting to its use.	Softonics	Free to download	Windows	1-many	1	3+ hours	Creativity, problem solving, user interaction, platform game design and user generated content (development skills)	Easy to use Relaxing Multiple games to choose from	Research-oriented Transversal

Name	Description	Publisher	Cost	Accessibility	Players	Language Support	Gameplay Time	Skills	Game Features	UPSKILLS Domain Clusters
<u>Storybook Brawl</u>	This game is targeted towards those people who show a preference to card games. It is a strategy game which is played through deck creation. The card game which features a number of creatures and treasures is an auto battler game, and each of the characters has a well defined role which makes game play slightly easier to grasp especially for beginners. Reviews indicate a game that is fun to play, with a good storyline and therefore quite appealing to the UPSKILLS target audience.	Good Luck Games LLC	Free to play	Windows	1	1	2-3 hours	Strategy	Easy to use Card game Fun Strategy	Research-oriented Transversal
<u>If on a Winter's Night, Four Travellers</u>	This game is focused around a narrative, and uses the point-and-click type of adventure game. It contains an element of horror, whilst exploring the stories of 4 different characters as they travel on a train. The story unfolds in the 1920's. The game also explores certain themes such as homophobia, racism, mental illness, etc so can be used to stimulate a degree of discussion amongst themes.	Dead Idle Games	Free to play (certain content is released at a price)	Windows	1	1	2-3 hours	Creativity	Adventure, Point & Click game (easy to use) Narrative Can provoke discussion	Intercultural Research-oriented Transversal
<u>Loading Story</u>	A very short game revolving around the narrative of a young software developer who is trying to keep her job. It's another point and click game, that is built mostly along dialogue.	Potatodog	Free	Windows	1	1	20-30 mins	Communication	Narrative Fun Short	Research-oriented Organisational Transversal
<u>Rising Spire: Prelude</u>	A fantasy game set around mystery and adventure, as a young character sets out on a journey across the world of Malus. This game is a prelude and an introduction to the actual game Rising Spire which is not free. However this game can also be used as a standalone game, that encourages exploration, character interactions and asset collection. This game will attract people who like role-playing games with a good narrative at the backend.	LFB Studios	Free	Windows	1	1	2-3 hours	Communication Interaction	Narrative Role-playing	Research-oriented Transversal
<u>Robot Daycare</u>	This game is built as a visual novel and it shows the perspective of 4 young people intent on raising a robot. This game may provoke a number of discussions around various themes in Ethics of AI and may be used to launch a face-to-face discussion in class. Game endings may vary drastically depending on the in-game decisions by the players.	Kigyodev	Free	Windows	1	1	1-2 hours	Communication Interaction	Narrative Engaging Short Provokes discussion	Research-oriented Organisational Transversal
<u>13:Origin - prologue</u>	This game is a typical escape room game where the player needs to solve puzzles to get out of a locked room in a mental institution. There is a storyline that evolves through the solution of the puzzles, which although not too easy are not impossible to solve. The game is meant to be a single-player game but it can also be played as a group/team activity, to elicit problem solving skills.	Corvus Studio, Inc	Free	Windows	1	2	3+ hours	Problem-solving Logic	Narrative Puzzle solving	Research-oriented Transversal
<u>Markus Ritter - The lost Family</u>	This is a game that's a recollection of games from the 1990's with full-motion video displaying the action in the game. This game is another puzzle game, which can be either played as it is meant to be (single player) or else use class groupings to help users engage more with the story content and solve puzzles together. This game can also elicit some further discussions and interactions amongst players as they traverse the game narrative.	Flimmersoft	Free	Windows	1	2	1-2 hours	Problem-solving	Narrative Short	Intercultural Research-oriented Transversal

Name	Description	Publisher	Cost	Accessibility	Players	Language Support	Gameplay Time	Skills	Game Features	UPSKILLS Domain Clusters
<u>Blackhaven</u>	This game is a first-person narrative game designed around a historic setting. The young character Kendra Turner explores a historic site she happens to be working at, to unravel clues and stories belonging to past era. The game presents an interesting and engaging narrative, together with graphics and visuals of artistic artefacts and paintings. The game is also interesting because it combines efforts from game developers as well as history scholars and elicits possible discussion points from the perspective of the development of history.	Historiated	Free	Windows	1	1	2-3 hours	Problem-solving Interaction	Historic Story-rich	Data-oriented Research-oriented Transversal
<u>Faded Grey</u>	This game is another visual novel told in first person, as the player moves around a house, trying to unravel mysteries of his past childhood. This walking simulation features music and graphics which help increase immersion into the story. This is a short game that might have some horror elements though it's not scary.	Derek Gollither	Free to play	Windows	1	1	15-30 mins	Communication	Narrative Short	Intercultural Research-oriented Transversal
<u>Data Horror Escape Room</u>	This game is a web-based version of an escape room with puzzles related to the handling of data in research which are needed to be solved in order to proceed in the game. It is a game which needs an online connection to be played, and which is played individually. Game play time can vary according to how fast puzzles are solved.	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Leiden University and Eindhoven University of Technology	Free to play	All platforms	1	1	2-3 hours	Research Data Management	Narrative Puzzles	Research-oriented Data-oriented
<u>Research Data Management L'Adventure Game</u>	This game is web-based storyline game, which uses the player's given answers to proceed through the game. In this game, the player is assuming the role of a staff researcher working at a university. The game makes use of a narrative to take the player through a sequence of events which require him/her to make a decision or take an action depending on the task he/she is given.	University of Bath in collaboration with Stellenbosch University	Free to play	All platforms	1	1	1-2 hours	Research Data Management	Narrative Question/ Answer	Research-oriented Data-oriented
<u>Dans Data Game</u>	This is an online version of a card game that is played in groups of 3-4. In this game, each player has a set of cards and he/she needs to build a quartet of cards with research-oriented goals. For example the player needs to gain a set of 4 cards related to 'Why Share Data'. In order to complete a set of 4 cards, called a quartet the player, needs to guess who out of the other players has the card that he/she needs.	Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data	Free to play	All platforms	3-4	2	30mins-1 hour	Research Data Landscape	Card Game	Research-oriented
<u>Lives in Transit</u>	This game is played over the web and is platform independent. It consists of 4 role-playing games, where the player needs to take on the role of a University post-graduate student grappling with research. Its series of questions-answers take the player across the narrative which gradually unfolds as the student answers correctly. Answers can take the form of emails, point and click answers, multiple choice, note taking, etc.	University of Zurich	Free to play	All platforms	1	1	30mins-2 hours	Post-graduate research	Narrative Question/ Answer	Research-oriented Data-oriented

Table 1. Off-the-Shelf Games List

Name	Description	Cost	Accessibility	Players	Language Support	Gameplay Time	Skills	UPSKILLS Domain Clusters
ArtBot	A game that aims to teach concepts of reinforcement learning and more specifically supervised learning. The game shows how different parameterisation can affect an output's accuracy when choosing between two different objects.	Free	Windows Web	1	2	20-30mins	Machine Learning Reinforcement Learning	Technical
<u>Minecraft Learns ML</u>	A game that aims to show concepts of neural networks using imitation learning, as part of machine learning. In the game, players create a basic ML dataset and decide on the architecture of a neural network to solve navigation problems.	Free	Windows	1	2	20-30mins	Neural Networks Imitation Learning	Technical
<u>Super Meat Bot</u>	SupermeatBot is a game that also teaches about Reinforcement Learning in Machine Learning. In this game, players design the levels with rewards and deterrents which the AI will have to learn from to be able to traverse across the obstacles successfully. This is an easy, fun and engaging game.	Free	Windows	1	2	20-30mins	Reinforcement Learning Design & Creativity	Technical Transversal
Data Agent	This game uses data generated from Wikipedia and DBpedia to generate an adventure. Players will follow the storyline to read up and solve the puzzles for the story to unfold.	Free	Windows Mac Web	1	1	20-30mins	Narrative Logic	Data-oriented Research oriented Transversal

Table 2. IDG Games List

Name	Description	Cost	Accessibility	Players	Language Support	Gameplay Time	Skills	UPSKILLS Domain Clusters
The Maze Game	A game that aims to reinforce Machine Learning concepts through a maze-like quiz based game.	Free	Windows Mac	1	1	10-15mins	Machine Learning	Technical
The Cube Game	A game that aims to increase confidence in programming skills through giving text based commands to move and shift cubes around the screen to proceed to different levels.	Free	Windows	1	2	30mins-1hour	Programming/Coding	Technical

Table 3. Games Designed for UPSKILLS

2.2 Game choice rationale

The games proposed in the game list for the UPSKILLS Curriculum have been chosen mostly for the attributes which make them resonate with the preferences identified by linguistics students in relation to games and gameplay.

Amongst the preferred attributes, the ones which have been given more prominence include the brevity of game play (games that last between 30mins to 3 hours have been given preference), the narrative and the game plot, as well as the targeted skills (such as problem solving, creativity, data management, etc.). Priority was also given to games that were released as free versions, or that were created as academic resources due to the fact that this project is supported by EU funds, and these are some of the project funding requirements. Therefore, games in data management and coding featured in this regard.

The games that feature in the list that has been compiled specifically for UPSKILLS have attributes that resonate with the aforementioned UPSKILLS needs analysis. Tables 2 & 3 of this report give detailed information about the learning outcomes in relation to the domain clusters as emergent from the needs analysis for the development of the language specialist profile.

In addition to the domain clusters featuring in UPSKILLS, the list of games includes information about the game: description, publisher, cost, accessibility, number of players, number of languages supported, time for play, supported skills and main game features. The game features have been chosen in line with the user preferences according to the survey in Section 2.

One of the issues which was always discussed amongst project team members was the importance of making use of games which do not propagate the notion of traditional content testing. However from feedback collected from the various project consortium meetings, it was concluded that there was room to include a game that can provide some form of self test or assessment regarding content but which does not impinge on the formal course assessment. Such checks could be used throughout for students to get small chunks of feedback based on the content which they covered. In this way, project partners responsible for content development felt that by having a game which can have an editable form of content would be ideal so they could be free to add specific content according to the classes they run.

Two games were developed by the Department of AI, University of Malta, to satisfy these needs. The first game is a simple maze game which was designed, using Unity as a game development platform to simulate quizzing in a gamified environment. The game is presented through a first person perspective navigating a maze where junction walls are defined by a set of questions to which there is either a right or a wrong answer. The Unity development files and sources are shared amongst the consortium, however, according to feedback in the subsequent evaluation component of the project this might be developed further to include an easy to use editor for content questions and feedback to be added or

edited. In this way, we could also include more levels to the game to increase the level of complexity and the duration of play. However for the scope of this project as well as the evaluation of the impact of games on learning, this is left open to future developments in the project.

The second game which was developed was slightly more of a technical nature where gameplay is defined by programming skills, in selecting the correct answer and selecting the right suite of commands to overcome obstacles and reach the goal in the level. The game interface consists of cubes which the user needs to move around to achieve the correct answer and move to the next level. The user also needs input text commands to be able to move the cubes and thus move on to the next level. The game is challenging because the user needs to familiarise herself/himself with the various data commands so that the play can proceed. However the users are also engaged in the game through the narrative that has been included at the start. The game has been given a retro simple interface that is used to highlight the programming/textual coding aspect and at the same time provide a visual component to accompany the textual part.

3. Guide for including games in UPSKILLS curricula

3.1 Games for learning - Guidelines for academics/educators

A number of games which deal specifically with programming, data and research management have been selected from the list of games attached and a proposal for how these could be integrated in specific classes or modules is given. Each guideline carries the same format and structure so as to ensure cohesion and flow during class implementation.

For each example, academics and educators have information pertaining to the domain clusters, skills targeted during game play as well as learning outcomes which intersect with the UPSKILLS needs analysis. This would make it easier to choose which module or class the game would best be adapted for and which would carry the more meaningful experience during teaching and learning. One of the most important aspects of using games during the teaching/learning experience is that of allowing the time for a pre- and post-game briefing - that is a period of reflection. It is strongly recommended that enough time is allocated for these briefing sessions as these will support the skills, competences and knowledge that are in line with the scope of the module or class given. It will also serve to clear up any misconceptions that might result from any solo-led learning activity.

The questions proposed below aim to create a sense of self-awareness in students that would lead towards a reflection about the skills, competences and knowledge that they possess or which they have gained through the actual game play.

Game Example #1:

Assignment 42: https://store.steampowered.com/app/1641580/Assignment_42/

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Research-oriented
- Technical (optional as an introduction to programming)
- Transversal

Target Audience:¹

Undergraduate / postgraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Understanding of language technology
- Analytical skills
- Logical skills
- Problem-solving skills
- Teamwork and communication skills
- Working under pressure

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Have acquired a basic knowledge of programming (using visual programming)
- Demonstrate an ability to understand technology terminology and some related tools
- Gain an understanding of data management
- Refine their problem-solving skills through independent learning

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

¹ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

This is a game that introduces the concept of programming a bot to carry out a series of tasks leading to the final game mission. The game in itself can take a few hours to play, but the concept of the game can be grasped in the first hour or so of play. This game can be assigned either as a game to be played from start to finish, and thus get more confident with programming and computational thinking skills, or else it can also be played in part to support teamwork, working under pressure, and developing communication skills.

The story unfolds as the students carry out more programming tasks. At first, the instructions are rather scanty, and the game's purpose might not be as revealing. However, this becomes more apparent with more game play.

The overall purpose of playing this game, is that of having students gain a better understanding into a form of algorithmic thinking for the purpose of solving a given task. However, this game can also be used to help them improve on soft skills such as paying attention to detail, independent learning and problem-solving.

Although game play is single-player, if this is given as a group activity, in class or outside class, this can also help develop increased communication skills among the group, through a discussion of the possible solutions to achieve the set missions.

Pre-Game Briefing:

The game you are assigned is called Assignment 42. This is a game where you are tasked with solving a number of programming-related puzzles to solve assignments which will lead you to achieve the final mission. The game's overall story is also described in the first scene of the game, and instructions are also ongoing throughout the game. The basic narrative is that you find yourself in a futuristic research lab and you need to instruct your bot on how to solve specific assignments to deal with problems and challenges that seem to be present in the lab.

The game can take up to a few hours of play. If you are playing this on your own, it is suggested that you focus on how you can make your bot follow instructions to carry out its task. If you are playing this in a team, it is suggested that you balance out your team with people having experience as gamers or as programmers. If this game is played in teams, you are required to record the number of missions you have managed to solve in 30mins. Teams will be challenging each other depending on which team solves the more missions in the given 30mins.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- Was it single play or did you play in a team?
- How was game play? Can you describe the game mission and the game rules?
- Did you achieve more than 1 mission?

Possible discussion questions to raise as part of a programming class

- This game uses a type of programming that is not based on a specific language. It is referred to as visual programming.
- Reflect a bit about it. What can you say about it? Is it clear? Is it confusing? What is it trying to achieve?
- What particular terms or terminology have you come across which are also part of the programming terminology?
- What is common between the two (the programming language you are familiar with and this game?)

Possible discussion questions to raise as part of a management class (including and applying to transversal skills)

- What problem were you attempting to solve during the game?
- On a scale from 1-10 with 10 being most difficult, how difficult was it to arrive to a solution and solve the mission?

Possible discussion questions to raise if game is played in teams

For academics and lecturers: It is recommended that if the game is played using teams, it is done as an in-class activity and that the activity is timed (for example teams are given 30mins to see which team solves the most missions). In addition it is recommended that teams are set up in terms of gaming/programming experience and that the more experienced players or programmers are asked to join different groups. The following are the suggested discussion questions for team play:

- Did playing in teams help solve the game quicker or more efficiently? Why or why not?
- Reflect a bit about your game play in the team. What communication strategies did you use to help make solving missions more efficient and effective?
- Which strategies would you keep or which ones would you remove to be able to play more efficiently next time and complete as many missions as possible?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- How did this game serve your objective during the UPSKILLS course?
- If you were to use it again, would you change anything in the way the game was inserted in the course program and curriculum?

- Would you have the students play this game once, or play it continuously as part of the ongoing course development?

Game Example #2:

Developer Inc.: https://store.steampowered.com/app/1612540/Dev_Inc/

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Research-oriented
- Organisational
- Transversal

Target Audience:²

Undergraduate / postgraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low

Skills Targeted:

- Analytical skills
- Ability to review a problem, identify a solution and foresee opportunities
- Project management skills
- Planning skills
- Teamwork and communication skills

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Demonstrate skills related to analytical reasoning
- Identify the problem related to the task at hand, and think of possible alternative solutions
- Creatively devise novel solutions to help maximise the solution's effectiveness
- Acquire project management skills involved in the setting up a successful startup in the area of game design

² This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

- Use their planning skills to foresee any challenges related to the setting up of the fictitious company
- Use effective marketing and development strategies for the success of the game designed and developed by the fictitious company

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

This is a game that mimics real life strategy in the formation of a successful technology startup. The objective of the startup is that of designing and developing a successful game to be launched to the market. This is a game that involves strategy more than just exploration, or other game mechanics. The players will work on a point and click method. The game, although marketed as a single-player game, would be ideal to be played in teams as there is the possibility of increasing the discussion about the setting up of a project and about elements that make up successful game design and development. This will also support teamwork, and therefore help users engage more in communication and interpersonal skills.

Although the target audience are not necessarily delving into game design, the technical jargon is one which can help them familiarise with other technical project management jargon, and will help them acquire soft skills related to leading successful projects whilst evaluating market expectations.

Pre-Game Briefing:

The game you are playing today is called Developer Inc. This is what is called a simulation environment game where you have to take the lead into a small startup company, to help design and develop a successful game that is launched on the market.

The game can take up to a few hours of play. Your scope is that of creating a game which is successful on the market. You need to decide what works and what doesn't but you also need to decide for your employees. You need to decide about their working conditions, what training would best work, and how in the end, you can maintain a good return on investment. If you play this in teams, you need to make sure that you have a consensus among the team player about which direction to take in the best interest of the employee/s and for the successful launch of the game you are designing and developing. Therefore you need to emphasise good communication between the team players and agree on the right strategy for developing this game.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- What game did you choose to develop?
- Did you go back and decide on a different strategy during your game play?
- Was your game successful on the market?

- Can you describe what strategies you have used to:
 - Design the game?
 - Train your employees?
- Was it single play or did you play in a team?

Possible discussion questions to raise to develop research & organisational skills:

- What steps did you start with to determine the type of game to develop?
- What problems/challenges did you encounter?
- What strategies did you think about to overcome those challenges?
- How did you manage your project overall? What plans did you have in place and how did those plans develop over time?

Possible discussion questions to raise to help develop transversal skills (in case of team play):

- What communication techniques did you choose during your team (face-to-face) game play?
- What different roles have been taken up within your team/group?
- On a scale from 1-10 with 10 being most difficult, how difficult was it to learn how to play this game, with a degree of success?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- Was this game useful in the class that you have taught?
- Are the skills described in this guide well addressed during game play? If not, why do you think has this happened?
- Does this game have other potential skills that it can help develop?
- Would you have the students play this game individually or in teams? Why or why not?

Game Example #3:

Tales of Escape: https://store.steampowered.com/app/587860/Tales_of_Escape/

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Research-oriented
- Transversal

Target Audience:³

Undergraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Intermediate-Advanced

Skills Targeted:

- Analytical skills
- Ability to review a problem, identify a solution and foresee opportunities
- Teamwork
- Working under pressure
- Communication skills
- Attention to Detail

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Demonstrate skills related to analytical and logical reasoning to solve a series of puzzles
- Identify the problem related to the task at hand, and think of a possible solutions
- Work in a team, leading or taking a follower's role where and when necessary
- Demonstrate abilities to work under pressure to be able to solve the game's puzzles and escape from the room

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

This is a VR-based game that simulates an escape room. The strength of this game is that it can support multi-playing up to 6 persons. This means that it is ideal to support transversal skills such as communication and interpersonal skills. This game also uses the time element to introduce an extra challenge and have players work under pressure. Players are expected to solve puzzles to be able to escape from the game environment. This means that through this game, the educator can engage users in employing logic and reasoning to solve the challenges whilst attempting to unlock the game's escape point. This game has a number of additional scenarios which can be added. The additional scenarios are at a fee.

³ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

However the basic game is free and can be played in 30mins-1hour which makes it ideal as an in-class activity (especially if no VR sets are used, and users play using the PC).

Pre-Game Briefing:

The game you are playing today is a simulation of an escape room. This game can be played either via PC or on VR headsets. The concept is for you to team up in groups of up to 6 players to solve challenges and puzzles and manage to escape in the time set. You will need to use all your analytical and logical powers to be able to solve the puzzles. However this is not a 1-man show. You are expected to work with your team mates and assume leader or follower roles depending on the context and nature of the puzzle that needs to be solved. It is important that before making decisions, a consensus is reached and the solution is found avoiding in-group conflicts. You will be working under pressure and your attention to detail and sharp observation powers will be called in action. Work together to help make your escape out of this tale.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- Did you manage to escape?
- How long did it take you to escape?
- What did you think of the way your team worked to be able to escape (or not) ?
- Do you think that if you were to play this again you would assume different strategies to solve the puzzles?
- Which puzzle was most challenging and why?
- Which puzzle proved to be least challenging and why?

Possible discussion questions to raise to highlight transversal skills:

- How did you, as a team decide on the solutions to the puzzles?
- Was there just one leader in the team or did the team members assume leadership roles at various stages of game play?
- Were there any communication challenges you came across? What were they? Can you describe why it was a challenge?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- This game's strength was in team play. Do you agree?

- Do you think that the game was useful in developing logical and analytical skills in students?
- Do you think this game was enjoyable for the students whilst at the same time developing key target skills?
- Did you observe the team's communication strategies during gameplay. What were your observations?
- Did the time pressure affect the teams' decisions?

Game Example #4:

Runescape: <https://store.steampowered.com/app/1343400/RuneScape/>

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Research-oriented
- Organisational
- Transversal

Target Audience:⁴

Undergraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low-Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Ability to review a problem, identify a solution and foresee opportunities
- Project Management skills
- Planning skills
- Problem-solving skills
- Attention to detail

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Demonstrate skills in planning and managing in-game resources

⁴ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

- Identify challenges and work around devising alternative solutions to the problems identified
- Make use of logic and reasoning to solve the challenges provided by the game efficiently
- Demonstrate an ability to learn independently and efficiently making use of online communities and additional resources to achieve increased mastery of the game

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

This is a massively multiplayer role-playing game that offers players an experience which can extend to more than just an exploration of a magical environment. Players can choose their own characters and each character comes with his/her own set of skills, which he/she can use to complete the journey across the land. This means that if players do not like games in which characters have to fight, they might choose a character that has another role such as an alchemist for potion making or farming. What this game proposes is the development of a thinking whereby the players are given challenges and they have to creatively devise ways in which to solve those challenges within the given context they are traversing. Therefore this game is not a game that is played in a hurried environment and it is best if students are encouraged to play it at home, in a more relaxed environment. Students can be encouraged to join clans (or other groups) that would also enhance their communication and interpersonal skills.

Pre-Game Briefing:

Runescape presents a magical world through which you are invited to traverse. Runescape can be thought of as a journey across a kingdom made up of diverse environments. In this game you are free to choose your character, and the role your character can assume. You might choose to become a potion maker, or a farmer or to develop whatever skill you want to. You will then use this skill to solve challenges, to make new friends and companions and explore this magical kingdom. Runescape is defined as a MMORPG - meaning massively multiplayer online roleplaying game. This means that in Runescape you will find many players who will be playing their own game as they too take on their journey. It also means that you need to be online to play and that you play by taking on a role. This role is specific to the skills you want to acquire and develop, such as for example, that of a potion maker. There are a number of communities and video tutorials that show you how you can play Runescape too so it's up to you if you really want to master the game! The essential feature is that the game leaves it entirely up to you how or where you want to play. There is no fixed place where to start or a fixed destination. The scope of this game is to help you develop skills related to problem solving, independent learning, management and planning.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- How would you describe the experience of playing Runescape?
- What role did you choose to play and why?
- Did you meet or communicate with other players during your game play?
- Did you choose to meet people or did these encounters happen by coincidence?
- Did you pick a role which you decided to discard and then take up a different role? If yes why did this happen?
- Did you look up external sites, communities or game play videos whilst you were playing? Did you gain more information or did you get the help you needed?
- Can you describe some of the challenges you came across during your game play

Possible discussion questions to raise to highlight transversal skills:

- What ways or strategies did you use to solve the challenges you have come across? You can give different examples.
- How long did it take you to start learning the game?
- How long did it take you for you to start developing your in-game skills?
- Did you seek external help to solve challenges in the game?
- Following your game play, are there specific strategies you would suggest to someone who is starting to play the game?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- It is recommended that this game is played at home over a number of sessions/hours and that discussion follows in class after. Do you agree with this strategy? Why or why not?
- This game is an example of a role playing game that can help students acquire soft skills that go beyond the curriculum. From the class discussions, what sort of skills do you think that students have acquired by playing this game?
- Did you observe students discussing the game and its dynamics beyond the formal discussions set up by yourself during class time?
- How would you say students describe Runescape? Did you get any additional feedback about the game? Is this feedback useful to make use of in class, during discussions related to the rest of your curriculum?

Game Example #5:

Roblox: <https://roblox.en.softonic.com>

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Research-oriented
- Technical
- Transversal

Target Audience:⁵

Undergraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low-Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Ability to review a problem, identify a solution and foresee opportunities
- Ability to work with scripting & basic game design
- Communication skills
- Planning skills
- Problem-solving skills
- Independent learning

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Demonstrate skills in designing and scripting for a basic game
- Demonstrate an ability to learn independently and efficiently making use of online communities and additional resources to achieve increased mastery of the game
- Communicate effectively with others to play and/or create games
- Use logic to solve in-game puzzles
- Employ creative skills to design new games
- Use strategic thinking to create new game settings and scenarios

⁵ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

There are two ways that students can play this game. One way in which this game can be exploited is through free play. The free Roblox game is available for Windows and Android and offers a platform of different games which students are free to choose from. Students can choose to play the genres which they prefer, using creativity, strategy and game-playing skills to complete the mini-games chosen. One way in which lecturers can work with this is to let students choose their own game, and ask them to play the game in groups of 2 or 3. The students are asked to assign each other roles whilst playing, and to discuss ways of play which they have agreed on. In this way, you would be potentially exploiting the development of communication skills, as students play games together. Such skills would also include effective planning and management of team efforts. In this case, it is also important to let students choose the games they want to play themselves. In this way they would be encouraged to follow independent learning.

The second way in which this game can be exploited is by having students download Roblox Studio, and encourage students to work in groups and through scripting create their own games. There are a number of online tutorials and game design videos on YouTube that can help students get started with scripting and designing.

The students can be given 4-5 weeks to come up with their own game design, scripting objects and working to insert some form of action. The game which they produce will be played by other teams and teams/groups will give feedback to each other. Throughout the period of game design, students can have small group discussion sessions to discuss the challenges they are finding, and the game which they are in the process of designing with their tutor and colleagues. It is ideal if the students find some time to attend some game design tutorials. It has to be said that this is not a game design course and it is not the aim to produce game designers. The main objective is that of enhancing the students' confidence in the use of technology-driven platforms, that make use of scripting processes as this has an impact on skills related to programming. Therefore, the final aim should not be in the final game product itself, but rather on the communicative and creative process involved in its development.

Pre-Game Briefing:

Roblox is played in two distinct ways. You can choose to pursue either way or both, depending on your curriculum and proposed course learning outcome.

#1 Game play to support logic, communication & team work

You are asked to download Roblox and install it. You will be asked to sign up and create a login for your account. Roblox is free to download on Windows PC and Android as well as Apple iOS (iPhone and iPad).

Roblox is a platform which offers a broad range of games of varying genres. You are asked to join teams with other 2 or 3 students and explore a number of games together. In this exercise you are asked to:

- Set up roles within your group as you start playing games (a leader, a researcher (of game play strategies), a communicator (form part of online communities related to the games chosen));
- Choose games to play (you can visit: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1220905/roblox-most-visited-games/> to have an idea of the more popular games in 2021)
- Choose 2 or 3 genres of games on Roblox and note down your observations on game play.

#2 Game play to support creativity, independent learning and the ability to script new game scenarios.

You are asked to download Roblox Studio and install it. You can use your Roblox login if you already have one. If not you will be asked to sign up for it. For this particular use of Roblox you are asked to join in groups of 2 or 3 and you will be asked to work together for the next 5 weeks.

You will have 4 weeks to design a simple new game from scratch using Roblox studio. You are not expected to design and develop a complex game but you might even create a small exploratory 3D Virtual World. You are also invited to find a number of online tutorials about how you can create worlds and scenarios in Roblox. The scope of this exercise is for you to gain more independence in your learning, to work effectively in a team, and to create a project which you can share with your audience.

Game de-Briefing (post-play #1):

- Can you describe the games that you chose to play in Roblox?
- Why did you choose them?
- For your group play, did you set up different roles to help with game play?
- If you have assigned roles, do you think this made your game play more or less efficient?
- Were you able to reach a consensus about the games that you played, or how you played them?
- Which was the most challenging game? Why?
- Which game elements make a game more successful in your opinion?
- How long did you take playing each game? Why did you choose to play for this amount of time?
- Would you say that beyond this course, you would continue to play Roblox for leisure?

Game de-Briefing (post-play #2):

- Did you manage to create a simple game scenario using Roblox studio?
- Can you describe what you created?
- What was the biggest challenge in creating this scenario?
- Did the fact that you were working in a team help or hinder this development?
- Do you plan on expanding this game scenario to include more complex game play?
- Following this exercise of using Roblox for our course, do you think you will take up playing Roblox more frequently? Do you think that you would be interested in continuing to develop your skills in creating Roblox games?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- It is recommended that this game is played for 4/5 weeks and that discussion follows in class after. Do you agree with this strategy? Why or why not?
- This game offers two ways of play - there is that form of play that would support the usual game play strategy and winning tactics, and there is that form of play that supports creativity. Do you think that for the purposes of UPSKILLS you would promote one over the other? Which form of game play would you promote?
- Did you look at the students' creations in Roblox? Do you think that those creations reflect the students' research orientation and directions?
- Do you think there is potential and scope to exploit Roblox in different ways to suit the needs of students and researchers in UPSKILLS?

Game Example #6:

Storybook Brawl: https://store.steampowered.com/app/1367020/Storybook_Brawl/

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Research-oriented
- Transversal

Target Audience:⁶

⁶ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

Undergraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low-Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Ability to review a problem, identify a solution and foresee opportunities
- Planning & strategy skills
- Problem-solving skills

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Use strategic thinking to come up with best play, even when there are random circumstances that might make it difficult to plan ahead
- Show more advanced adaptation skills as they continuously aim to master the game
- Learn play strategies and tactics against an AI driven agent

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

This game is promoted as an autobattler game where the player is going to battle against an AI component using cards. There is no fighting but there is a lot of strategy involved in this game so it encourages and supports higher level thinking, problem solving but also adaptation to randomness as the game unfolds. The randomness ensures that the players do not get too comfortable with routine play but are constantly thinking about ways in which to beat the AI agent. This game is suggested more as a home activity rather than a class-based activity because skills need to evolve over time and players, especially newcomers to these sort of card battling games, need time to familiarize themselves and sharpen their skills. Even though one game may take 1-2 hours of play, it is suggested that students are advised to play this game for 2-3 weeks, to possibly refine their game play and strategy. One question that can be asked during the discussion is about the development of strategy skills to raise more awareness of the students' problem solving abilities.

Pre-Game Briefing:

This game is an auto battler card game. You will play individually, though you can always choose to play socially in groups of two. In this game you are playing against an AI that is randomly choosing different cards in order to win. You have to choose the first initial

hero card that you will be playing with but beyond that you have to strategically plan your moves around the random cards that you will be getting. The main goal is to have your character as the last person standing out of the 8 characters who are initially in the game. You will have different characters come up as you traverse the game, and you will have spells that help your hero get stronger. The more opponents you fell down the stronger your hero gets. This is a game of strategy and tactics. It might be that at first you will need to learn the ropes, so you might lose a few battles. But the aim is that the more you play, the more you sharpen your strategic skills and problem solving abilities in the face of randomness.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- What word would you say best describes this game?
- Can you identify the sort of strategies which you were using to win against different opponents?
- Would you say that your gameplay changed throughout the game?
- Did you find that the more you played it the stronger your game play turned out?
- Would you say that strategy-wise this game helped you improve your skills?
- Do you think that randomness was a crucial and determining factor in the game play?
- Did randomness help or hinder your play?
- Do you think the outlook of the characters reflected your decision-making during the game?
- What challenges do you attribute to this game?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- It is recommended that this game is played at home over a number of sessions/hours and that discussion follows in class after. Do you agree with this strategy? Why or why not?
- This game is not strictly tied to a fixed curriculum and it helps the students acquire more general skills in terms of strategy and problem solving. What do you think of this? Do you think this is useful?
- How important do you think that strategy and problem-solving are for your course but also for the profession of the language data specialist?

Game Example #7:

If on a Winter's Night, Four Travellers:

https://store.steampowered.com/app/1603980/If_On_A_Winters_Night_Four_Travelers/

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Intercultural
- Research-oriented
- Transversal

Target Audience:⁷

Undergraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low-Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Ability to understand different local contexts
- Ability to localise content in accordance with cultural differences
- Processing information critically
- Problem-solving skills
- Communication skills

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Have understood the context of play through the game narrative
- Identified with the different characters and their behaviours through game play and identify how different cultures may react to different situations in different ways
- Use problem-solving skills to solve the puzzles as they appear during game play
- Reflect on the context of the game character lives and use them to draw up specific lessons learned

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

⁷ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

This game is a narrative point and click game. There are no specific skills that are required from the players, however it is a game that is very much dependent on the players' understanding of the unfolding narrative. It is expected that students would have a good mastery of the language in a way that they can understand and empathise with the characters and their respective stories. The game is quite short and can be played in 2-3 hours.

Pre-Game Briefing:

This game is a narrative point and click game. It is also quite short and the main scope is that of exploring the stories of four different travellers at a masked ball on a train in the 1920s. During this game you are asked to pay attention to the unfolding of the stories as they emerge, the language which they communicate their oftentimes poignant stories, and the flow attached to the plot. You are also encouraged to think about alternative endings to these stories but also to reflect about how stories from other characters would merge into this game.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- What are your thoughts about the language used within this game to communicate the narratives and the characters' stories?
- What other genres of stories would such a use of language apply to?
- If the setting of the game and the story were to change would such a language still be appropriate?
- Would you say other stories would merge adequately with this?
- Have you provided alternative endings to this?
- If you had to design a sequel to this - in terms of the narrative, how would it look like?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- Do you think that this game has the potential to be of good use to the project UPSKILLS or to help develop creative or cultural skills in students?
- What feedback did you observe/obtain from the students who played this game?
- Do you think that you can add on additional methods to help students develop critical information processing skills?

Game Example #8:

Loading Story: https://store.steampowered.com/app/1721980/Loading_Story/

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Organisational
- Research-oriented
- Transversal

Target Audience:⁸

Undergraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low-Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Ability to understand different local contexts
- Ability to localise content in accordance with cultural differences
- Processing information critically
- Problem-solving skills
- Communication skills

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Have understood the game dialogue and completed the game
- Completed the mini games, and proceeded through the game

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

This is an extremely short game based on dialogue. The character is a girl living inside a computer having the role of loading games. The goal of this adventure game is that of having the player walk around the virtual game space, interact with the other characters, and play simple games. There are no quizzes or puzzles associated to this game and its strength is in the dialogue it offers.

⁸ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

Pre-Game Briefing:

This is a short adventure game about a character that is trapped inside a computer space. The goal of the character is that of loading computer games. However there are a number of requests that you might have to ignore to be able to proceed. The scope of the game is that of following the fast paced dialogue and act in the best way possible to proceed in the game.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- What are your overall thoughts about this game? Does the language flow adequately?
- What does the dialogue do for the game? What would the game be like without the dialogue?
- How does the style of language affect the game pace?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- Do you think that this game might be useful for language courses?
- Do you believe that this game can be used to stimulate some creative skills in students?

Game Example #9:

Research Data Management Adventure Game: <https://rdm-games.gitlab.io/rdm-adventure/>

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Research-oriented
- Data-oriented

Target Audience:⁹

Postgraduate

⁹ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low-Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Processing information critically
- Problem-solving skills
- Communication skills

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Have acquired skills related to research data management
- Understand how to take decisions related to project planning and research
- Understand how to choose instruments and tools for research
- Describe datasets and file organisation

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

This is a 1-2 hour role-playing game which immerses the player into the role of a researcher/post graduate student. This offers options for qualitative and experimental research. The player has to go through choices and decisions. A wrong decision will result in the game prompting the player until they take the right decision for the purpose of the game.

Pre-Game Briefing:

This is an online role-playing game where you are expected to take on the role of a researcher. You have the option to either choose a qualitative or an experimental path. You will be expected to take decisions according to the task at hand to be able to solve the challenge given.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- Did you choose qualitative or experimental research? What prompted you to choose that pathway?
- Describe and illustrate 2 data management strategies which you didn't make use of before and think of starting to adopt now or which you made use of, but still struck you as important after playing this game.
- After playing this game do you feel more confident in applying your research skills to practice?

- Did you feel that this game realistically represented research scenarios?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- Do you think that this game might be useful for language courses?
- Do you believe that this game is a simulation of the basic research process and that it will contribute to expanding or consolidating the students' knowledge?

Game Example #10:

Data Horror Escape Room: <https://sites.google.com/vu.nl/datahorror/home?authuser=0>

UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:

- Research-oriented
- Data-oriented

Target Audience:¹⁰

Postgraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low-Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Processing information critically
- Problem-solving skills
- Communication skills

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

¹⁰ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

- Have acquired a greater degree of confidence in some of their own research skills
- Have applied their creativity to solve problems
- Have acquired data management skills

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

This game is an online representation of an escape room game. It might take the students between 2-3 hours to be able to effectively solve all the clues and finish the game, though some students might find it easier. It is suggested that students work on this game in teams (2-3 students), although this can also be played individually. Playing in teams will also help them solve the escape room challenge in less time. Adding team work to the game will possibly target collaboration and leadership skills, as well as bring together possible diverse ideas from each group member. The game centres around a narrative of a researcher who is given short challenges to be able to solve the greater puzzle. Research takes on a mysterious dimension, whilst at the same time some of the problems which the player needs to solve, focus on research management skills such as ethical practices, administrative issues, and data management.

Pre-Game Briefing:

This is an online escape room game where you are expected to follow the clues and solve brief challenges/ tasks that will provide you with additional clues so that you can solve the mystery surrounding your research assignment. Challenges and tasks will mainly focus on data management and elements of the research process. It is suggested that your work together in groups of 2 or 3 and collaborate on solving the tasks assigned.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- Did you play individually or in teams? If you played in teams, did you elect a leader out of the team, or did all the members lead equally?
- Was there an aspect of data management that you felt was highlighted during this game?
- Did you feel that this game realistically presented research challenges?
- Which challenge do you feel was more difficult to solve and what made it so challenging?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- Do you think that this game might be useful for language courses?
- Do you believe that this game would be able to contribute to expand or consolidate the students' knowledge?

Game Example #11:**Lives in Transit:** <https://livesintransit.org/games>**UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:**

- Research-oriented
- Data-oriented

Target Audience:¹¹

Postgraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low-Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Processing information critically
- Problem-solving skills
- Communication skills

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Have acquired a greater degree of confidence in some research skills
- Have applied their creativity to solve problems
- Work together collaboratively to solve the given challenges

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

This game is a narrative-based game that combines real life data management situations with engaging scenarios. Lives in Transit has an additional feature that can be used by

¹¹ This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

academics to create their own storyline and scenarios to direct students' academic goals and learning outcomes. Throughout the game, the students as the players, will be expected to make choices based on their knowledge and understanding. Students are also encouraged to look up information in the process so as to support further learning practices. In this setting, students are encouraged to keep notes and to follow the branched storyline of the scenarios as they unfold. Students are expected to indicate their choices at the end of each scene for the game to progress.

Pre-Game Briefing:

In this game you will be faced with a number of scenarios, and each scenario will pose questions or choices which you need to answer or make in order to progress. Most often the scenarios will deal with research work in the field of history. You can also keep notes and keep track of the progress that you are doing within the game. One important aspect which you should consider is that your game's progress is saved so that you can return to your game play any time you feel like.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- Did you feel that this game realistically presented research challenges?
- Was there an aspect of data management that you felt was highlighted during this game?
- Did you feel that this game represented some of the more difficult choices you need/ed to make during your post grad studies?
- Which aspect of the game did you feel made the game more engaging?
- Which aspect of research do you feel did the game highlight the most?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- Do you think that this game might be useful in this format or would you consider customising it to accommodate a different module?
- Which type of module or course content would such a game adapt itself best to?
- Do you believe that this game would be able to contribute to expand or consolidate the students' knowledge?

Game Example #12:**The Maze Game: downloadable (.exe)****UPSKILLS Domain Cluster:**

- Technical

Target Audience:¹²

Undergraduate

Requirements:

No specific requirements

Gaming Experience:

Low-Intermediate

Skills Targeted:

- Machine Learning Knowledge

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of game play, the students are expected to:

- Have acquired a deeper knowledge into machine learning concepts
- Demonstrate increased confidence in their knowledge about machine learning concepts
- Have tested themselves about their knowledge of machine learning concepts

Introduction (for academics & lecturers):

This game is a simulation of a maze, where the students as players need to traverse a simple labyrinth by answering the questions correctly. At each labyrinth intersection the players are asked a question with 2 possible answers. The right answer leads to another intersection whilst the wrong answer leads to a dead end. The player's progress across the labyrinth is timed, to offer a greater challenge when answering the questions under the pressure of time. The end of the game is marked by exiting the labyrinth.

Pre-Game Briefing:

¹² This applies to students taking Linguistics & Language-related courses

In this game you will be launched in a labyrinth, with 10 intersections. Each intersection will present you with a question and 2 answers. One answer will lead you to a dead end. This means it's a wrong answer. One answer will lead you to the next intersection until you see the exit. Your labyrinth progress is timed. If you take too long to answer your time will expire and you will have to start from the beginning. You can take this labyrinth for as many times as you like. At the end you will be awarded with a progress badge.

Game de-Briefing (post-play):

- What machine learning concepts would you say that you weren't familiar with and are now more aware of after playing this game?
- Was there one particular concept which you couldn't grasp and which you would like to understand a bit more of?
- Following this game, is there any specific aspect of machine learning which you would like to learn more about and experiment with?

Conclusion (for academics & lecturers):

The following are a list of questions which you can make use of to evaluate the use of this game as part of your UPSKILLS course curriculum. You can use a journal to keep track of your answers.

- Add more questions to the labyrinth to help develop more levels and complexity;
- Which additional features to this game would make this more engaging?

4. Gamification of learning content

Gamification or what Jane McGonigal (2003) refers to as “gameful” design is an emerging field of practice that involves the use of game design and mechanics into non-gaming situations. We experience gamified situations like this everyday. These days plenty of coffee shops or fast food outlets gamify the eating experience by creating a system-based mental construct that entices players to buy more food for prizes or discounts which make the whole eating out/ coffee experience sound much more appealing. But rewards are not the only aspect of gamification. If you have ever read a story-based book that asked you to make a decision among a few choices so as to direct the story and provide multiple pathways to reach the end.

Gamification has many structural elements. In the classroom, they may include the following:

- **Creating a compelling storyline or narrative:** Powerful stories draw us in. When used in the classroom, gamification becomes a means of immersing students into an engaging narrative. Classroom imagination and storytelling spawn a new and exciting mental construct. Students are transported from their classrooms into a storyline. The content, assignments, assessments, and even the classroom procedures all take on the attributes of the storyline.
- **Autonomy:** Similar to games, when players have power to make decisions, they succeed or fail by their own choices. Educators must look for ways of placing decision-making in the hands of their learners.
- **Mastery of skills:** Gamification practices often reflect game design in allowing people to repeat the experience over and over again to master skills or review content. Repetition is a powerful learning strategy.
- **Immediate feedback:** Both positive and negative feedback should be provided in a timely manner. A fast-paced response allows the players to adapt quickly and overcome learning challenges.
- **Collaboration:** By promoting teamwork and community the individual needs of the learners are replaced by a combined focus on common goals.
- **Competition:** Individual learners or teams learn to face challenges under some pressure (time or peers).
- **Problem-solving:** Gamified learning environments most often present their learners with a problem to solve or a challenge to overcome. This engages the learner by involving them actively in their own learning. It is also important to take into consideration to level of difficulty of these challenges. A challenge that is too difficult to solve may prove to be too frustrating, one that is too easy may disengage the learners.
- **Differentiated learning experiences:** A gamified learning environment can provide learners with different pathways and different possibilities for learning. This means that learning can take a branched (non-linear) form, and not all learners are required to go through the same learning process at the same time.
- **The use of badges, points, and leaderboards:** Badges, points, and leaderboards are examples of how data can be provided to the learner to show his/her progress in the learning schema. Although these mechanisms are often lower-level feedback strategies, they are easy to implement and augment a gamification initiative when combined with other strategies (as listed above).

Game-based learning and gamification are not the same. Although each of these strategies has the potential to invigorate learning, game-based learning and gamification are distinctly different approaches to teaching, learning, and assessment. Whilst game-based learning involves the player learning or reviewing content or developing skills as they play a game, in gamification the educator emphasises the use of design to develop gaming elements in a non-gaming scenario.

Main Differences between Gamification and Game-based learning:

Gamification:

- Adding game inspired elements to your course
- Applying game mechanics to a non-game environment to encourage behaviour
- Typically incorporates badges, awards and achievements
- Experience points may be used as a substitute for traditional grades
- Could provide the students with choices in learning paths

Game-based learning:

- Using games to meet learning outcomes
- Learning comes from playing the game
- Could be accomplished using commercial or education oriented games
- Promotes critical thinking and problem solving
- Could be accomplished with both digital and non-digital games
- Might involve simulations to allow for greater experience of learning

5. Concluding remarks

This report illustrates different scenarios of how games can be included in the learning process, with particular attention to the content modules developed for the UPSKILLS project. Studies indicate that the use of games for learning is a widely established practice that is also being taken up for professional development. Using games does not necessarily mean that the game has been specifically designed and developed to include the curricular content. Off-the-shelf games can be made use of for a broader skill set, such as project management, communication and collaboration. However, game play has to be supported by a period of briefing and reflection for the players to achieve a stronger and deeper sense of self-awareness about the skills they possess or have acquired. In addition, there are other more specific serious games that use narrative and plot to involve learners in a series of decisions and choices which would lead them to a better understanding of the curricular content. Such games have the potential to direct learners to a more focused cognitive learning

path. However post-play reflection is always encouraged as part of the game-play exercise. In addition to game-based learning, gamification can also be applied to certain curricular modules. Gamification would involve the inclusion of game-elements to a non-gaming scenario. Therefore in a learning course, gamification may be added through a series of mini-competitions, or collaborative group work with added challenges that are time-dependent, at the end of which learners may receive badges or experience points as rewards or feedback.

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